

TAILORED FIBER PLACEMENT BASED ON EPOXY PREIMPREGNATED CARBON ROVINGS (TOWPREG)

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the process ability of an epoxy pre-impregnated carbon fiber roving (Towpreg) with the Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP) technology. TFP is a textile manufacturing technology for placing continuous reinforcement fibers (roving) in arbitrary directions. In this technology a single roving is fixated by a stitching yarn on a flat textile base material using a double locked stitch which enables the production of curvilinear fiber patterns with high degree of freedom. Originally, this technology was developed for placing non-impregnated (dry) roving material. Due to the availability of pre-impregnated roving material for filament winding these Towpreg materials in principle offers the opportunity to be placed within the TFP process as well.

Two different thermoset epoxy carbon Towpreg materials, (I) Mitsubishi Rayon Carbon Fiber and Composites CF 34-700 HMT 701 (MRC) and (II) TCR Composites Prepreg Tow UTS50 UF3330 (TCR), have been investigated for use within the TFP process regarding their process ability and their placement behavior. Relevant requirements concerning the tack of the Towpreg, process conditions, placement velocity and necessary modifications on the TFP device were identified.

To evaluate the effect of the TFP process on the mechanical properties of the Towpreg tensile strength and tensile modulus parallel and perpendicular to the fiber direction were determined experimentally. The measured strength and stiffness data are compared to the specified strength and stiffness properties of the raw Towpreg material.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their comparatively high density related strength and stiffness properties continuous FRP, especially CFRP, are used for structural parts in a wide range of application in order to save weight, energy and resources without trade-offs on durability and performance. Nowadays, CFRP parts with thermoset matrices are mostly manufactured based on dry fabrics (woven fabrics, non-crimp fabrics (NCF), braided fabrics) in which the resin is infiltrated subsequently, or based on resin pre-impregnated tapes or fabrics (e. g. filament winding, automated fiber placement). CFRP laminates are often designed and manufactured as stacked unidirectional (UD) layers with different angles of fiber orientation leading to quasi-isotropic stiffness and strength properties. In certain applications where only few dominant load cases occur conventional laminate stacking does not fully exploit the potential of the CFRP material. Furthermore, even small differences between load direction and fiber orientation cause a significant reduction of the mechanical properties, as shown in Figure 1. In order to minimize structural mass and to improve mechanical part properties a curvilinear fiber layout can be preferable.

Figure 1: Relative strength and stiffness of a CFRP laminate with unidirectional fiber orientation depending on the angle of the applied load direction

Figure 2: Basic principle of the TFP process

Spickenheuer investigated various methods to derive load adapted fiber paths in order to exploit the unidirectional properties of CFRP in structural parts [1]. For the production of curvilinear fiber patterns the Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP) technology was developed at the Leibniz-Institut für Polymerforschung Dresden e. V. TFP is a textile preform manufacturing technique which allows a flexible orientation of arbitrary reinforcement roving material (e.g. carbon, glass, aramid) [2]. Adapting embroidery technology, a single continuous roving is placed along programmable curves in a two-dimensional (2D) plane and fixated by a stitching yarn on a flat textile base material using a double locked stitch in a zigzag stitch pattern. The TFP principle is illustrated in Figure 2. The continuous fiber roving is oriented according to the design path by rotating the roving pipe and moving the base material in perpendicular directions.

Originally, the TFP Technology was developed for placing non-impregnated (dry) rovings. Thus, the production of structural parts made by TFP based preforms requires an additional resin infiltration process like e. g. resin transfer molding or vacuum assisted resin infusion.

Due to the commercial availability of pre-impregnated rovings (Towpregs) for filament winding, such Towpregs in principle open the possibility to be applied in the TFP process as well. Some of these Towpregs exhibit a sufficient shelf life at room temperature (up to 30 days), a constant fiber volume content and an adequate glass transition temperature needed to be applied in structural parts [3], [5]. A method for pre-staging such thermosetting Towpregs is described in [6].

The benefit of applying Towpregs in the TFP technology is manifold. The time consuming infiltration process has been omitted. Molds for curing do not require ports or valves for the resin infusion process and thus can be made less complex. Due to the homogeneous matrix volume content

within the Towpregs the risk of non-impregnated zones within the produced part is eliminated. The cutting of Towpreg based preforms is easier and more precise due to the matrix induced adhesion of the filaments compared to dry TFP preforms. If Towpreg materials are processed by stitching, the resulting material properties will be affected [7], [9]. In case of the TFP technology the displacement volume of the stitching yarn in combination with the zigzag stitch pattern causes a slight waviness of the reinforcement fibers in-plane and out-of-plane [8]. Furthermore, due to the added stitching yarn the fiber volume content is not distributed homogeneously and typically on average lower compared to unidirectional prepreg material that is perfectly aligned [10]. Consequently, the resulting fiber parallel modulus and strength of TFP preforms is lower compared to the unidirectional prepreg (reference material). The resulting material properties depend on the TFP process parameters stitch distance and stitch width and the diameter of the stitching yarn [8] [10]. If conventional thin stitching yarns are used and common TFP process parameters are applied, the reduction of the fiber parallel modulus due to the induced waviness is relatively low (up to 3 %, [10]).

On the other hand, the effect of the placement technology on the strength of the material is more pronounced. The inhomogeneous structure of the material leads to an irregular stress distribution within the roving. Depending on the process parameters this leads to a reduction of the fiber parallel strength up to 15 % compared to a perfectly aligned unidirectional material. Despite the relatively strong geometrical impact of the stitching yarn on the local stress levels it has to be emphasized that the final mechanical performance of these structural parts can be much higher compared to CFRP parts made of stacked UD prepreg layers. This behavior is the result of the high flexibility of the technology enabling the fibers to follow directly calculated load paths [3].

Due to the number of degrees of freedom regarding the fiber orientation the TFP technology offers the possibility to produce CFRP parts with significantly higher density related stiffness and strength properties compared to constructions based on conventional stacked CFRP laminates.

For the application of Towpreg materials in the TFP technology certain material characteristics are required. The placement process is carried out at room temperature. During the placement process no matrix material should be deposited on machine parts which are in contact with the Towpreg. Furthermore, the stitching yarn should not stick on the Towpreg to prevent stitching yarn failure. Thus a very low tack and an accordingly high viscosity of the resin are required.

Two different thermoset epoxy carbon towpreg materials, (I) Mitsubishi Rayon Carbon Fiber and Composites CF 34-700 HMT 701 (MRC) and (II) TCR Composites Prepreg Tow UTS50 UF3330 (TCR), have been investigated for use within the TFP process regarding their process ability and their placement behavior. To evaluate the effect of the TFP technology on the material properties of the processed Towpreg materials tensile tests on unidirectional Towpreg based specimen made by TFP were carried out.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Based on the pre-concluded requirements two different Towpreg materials were chosen and investigated. The properties of both Towpreg materials are shown in Table 1. Intentionally, these Towpreg materials were developed for the Filament Winding process.

Material	Unit	Mitsubishi Rayon Carbon Fiber and Composites (MRC)	TCR Composites (TCR)
Fiber type (Tow)		Carbon Grafil 34-700 - 12K-800 Tex	Carbon Toho Tenax UTS50-E13-12K-800Tex
Tow tensile modulus	$E_{f\parallel}$ [GPa]	234	240
Tow tensile strength	$R_{f\parallel}^+$ [MPa]	4830	4800
Tow fracture strain	$\varepsilon_{fr\parallel}$ [%]	2,0	2,0
Matrix type		Epoxy HMT 701	Epoxy UF3330
Glass transition temperature	T_g [°C]	120	120
Towpreg fiber volume content	φ_{Tow}	0,55	0,59
Towpreg shelf life at 20°C	[d]	30	30

Table 1: Raw material data of the investigated Towpreg materials

The comparison of the technical data of the MRC and the TCR Towpreg does not reveal any significant differences. Furthermore, both Towpreg materials are specified as low tack and look similar (see Figure 3 and Figure 4). In contrast to the comparable technical data the handling at standard climate (25 °C, relative humidity 65 %) is different. Compared to the TCR material the MRC Towpreg exhibits a lower tack and a better flexibility. Additionally, in case of the TCR Towpreg the resin tends to accumulate on the surface of the roving over time when it is stored at 25°C. It has to be mentioned that the resin content in the TCR material is 4 % higher compared to the MRC Towpreg.

After curing both Towpreg look a bit different when observed in a scanning electron microscope (cf. Figure 5 and Figure 6). The surface of the MRC Towpreg is covered with resin (smooth surface), while on the surface of the TCR Towpregs carbon filaments are visible (rough surface in comparison).

Figure 3: Detail view of the MRC Towpreg uncured

Figure 4: Detail view of the TCR Towpreg uncured

Figure 5 Scanning electron microscope picture of the cured MRC Towpreg

Figure 6: Scanning electron microscope picture of the cured MRC Towpreg

After evaluating the raw material optically and tactually the placement behavior of both materials were determined. All the TFP tests have been carried out on a Tajima TCWM-01 device at standard climate (25 °C, relative humidity 65 %) conditions. At the beginning, TFP tests were performed with a low stitch frequency of 100 stitches per minute. The Towpreg materials were fixed with a common 10 Tex polyester stitching yarn on a polyamide film. Despite the given specification the TCR material was not really capable for the TFP technology (see Figure 7). During the TFP process the resin accumulates on the surface of the Towpreg spool (see Figure 8) and during the TFP process the stitching yarn is covered with the resin as well. After a low number of stitches (< 100) the resin accumulates on the needle (Figure 10). Due to the high tack of the resin the force to pull the yarn through the hole in the needle exceeds the strength of the yarn and subsequently the yarn ruptured (Figure 9). The rupture of the yarn occurs approximately after 100 stitches even when the needle is cleaned or replaced as well.

Figure 7: Unidirectional placed TCR Towpreg with visible ruptured stitching yarn and inhomogeneous yarn tension

Figure 8: Resin accumulation on the surface of the Towpreg spool (TCR)

Figure 9: Resin covered needle with ruptured stitching yarn after the TFP process (TCR Towpreg)

Figure 10: Unused needle (top), Needle after TFP process based on TCR Towpreg (bottom)

In contrast to the behavior of the TCR Towpreg the TFP process based on MRC Towpreg is stable. No resin material is accumulated on the needle and thus no stitching yarn rupture occurred during the placement tests (Figure 11 and Figure 12).

Figure 11: TFP process with MRC Towpreg, no visible deposition of the resin on the needle

Figure 12: Unidirectional placed MRC Towpreg

At this stage it has to be mentioned that TCR material might be suitable for the TFP process when used at lower temperatures. When the TCR roving is cooled down just around 5 K to 20 °C it feels a lot less tacky and the tendency of the matrix accumulation on the Towpreg surface is non-existent anymore. Due to the ambient conditions in the lab the relatively large TFP device in the IPF could not be cooled down to 20°C. Thus, further placement tests with the TCR material have not been

conducted. Different stitch frequencies and different stitch parameters (variation of stitch width and stitch distance) were tested using the MRC Towpreg. Even at maximal stitch frequency (800 stitches per minute) the process is stable and comparable to dry roving materials.

Owing to the not suitable behavior of the TCR Towpreg in the TFP process at the given conditions, specimen to derive material properties were produced from the MRC Towpreg only. The tensile modulus and the tensile strength in fiber direction (fiber parallel) and perpendicular to the fiber direction (transverse) were determined experimentally according to standard DIN EN 527-5. For specimen production the MRC Towpreg was placed on a polyamide film. To achieve a symmetrical laminate structure two Towpreg preforms were placed back to back with the PA film on the outward face in one plate.

For the fiber parallel specimen a stitch width of 5 mm, a roving distance of 1.6 mm and a stitch distance of 2.2 mm were used to achieve a laminate thickness of 1 mm. For the transverse specimen the roving distance was changed to 0.8 mm and the stitch distance was adjusted to 1.2 mm to achieve a laminate thickness of 2 mm. After the TFP process both preforms were cured in a custom made evacuated mold which was placed in a hot press. The consolidation was performed as specified in the MRC data sheet (6 bar, 5 K/min ramp up to 130°C, hold for 90 min, cool down to 60°C, demold). With the applied cure cycle only a very small amount of resin (< 1%) was squeezed out of the preform. Thus, the resulting average fiber volume content after curing was 60 %. The achieved laminate quality was very good with no visible voids or local shrinkage effects (Figure 13). After demolding the plates stayed perfectly plane. To ensure a good bonding quality between the laminate and the necessary force transmission tabs the base material was removed prior applying the glass fiber reinforced plastic force transmission tabs.

Figure 13: Detail view, surface of the TFP made Towpreg plate after curing with visible lower stitching yarn and PA film

Figure 14: Detail view, surface of the TFP made Towpreg plate after removing the PA film.

Despite the low adhesion of the PA film on the cured laminate it was not possible to peel the film off the laminate which is a result of fixing the film with the stitching yarn. For this reason the film and partially the lower stitching yarn were removed in a careful executed grinding process. The surface of the Towpreg plate after the grinding process is shown in Figure 14.

After applying the tabs the specimen were cut to the specified length and width (10 mm width for fiber parallel tensile test, 20 mm width for transverse test). For each test 5 specimen were prepared (see Figure 15 and Figure 16).

Figure 15: TFP based Towpreg specimen for fiber parallel tensile tests

Figure 16: TFP based Towpreg specimen for tensile tests perpendicular to the fiber direction (transverse)

The tensile tests were performed on a TIRA test rig with a 100 kN load cell. The displacement rate was set to 1 mm/min for the transverse tensile test and 2 mm/min for the fiber parallel tensile test. The displacement was determined with an external position measurement system. In Figure 17 the specimen after the tensile test in fiber parallel direction are shown.

Figure 17: Unidirectional TFP based Towpreg (MRC) specimen after the tensile test in fiber parallel direction.

3 RESULTS AND DISSCUSION

The results of the tensile tests are shown in Table 2. The material data specified by the producer are listed as well. These material data were determined on perfectly aligned unidirectional material samples. Due to the numerically controlled placement process the mean variation of the determined data is comparatively low.

Engineering constant		Unit	Reference Value	Experimental TFP
Fiber volume content specimen	φ		0,6	0,6
Tensile modulus fiber parallel	E_{\parallel}	[GPa]	135,1*	125,3 ± 1,8
Tensile strength fiber parallel	R_{\parallel}^+	[MPa]	2530*	1885,3 ± 107,0
Fracture strain fiber parallel	$\varepsilon_{fr \parallel}$	[%]	-	1,56 ± 0,10
Tensile modulus perpendicular to the fiber direction	E_{\perp}	[GPa]	-	8,00 ± 0,07
Tensile strength perpendicular to the fiber direction	R_{\perp}^+	[MPa]	-	29,2 ± 1,42
Fracture strain perpendicular to the fiber direction	$\varepsilon_{fr \perp}$	[%]	-	0,38 ± 0,02

Table 2: Comparison of unidirectional MRC Towpreg (Mitsubishi Rayon HMT701 Grafil 34-700-12) raw material data and experimentally determined material properties of unidirectional TFP based MRC Towpreg. The comparison indicates and evaluates the influence of the TFP process on the resulting material properties. *not specified by the producer, calculated based on the fiber and matrix material data

Owing to the TFP induced inhomogeneity and waviness the resulting material properties are lower compared to the perfectly aligned state. In fiber parallel direction the tensile modulus is 7.5 % lower and the tensile strength is 25.4 % lower than in the ideal unidirectional state (Table 2).

The reduction of the fiber parallel modulus is higher than in TFP produced unidirectional CFRP based on dry rovings with almost identical fiber properties [10]. The reasons for that are diverse. As mentioned in [10] the fiber volume content is inhomogeneous due to the displacement volume of the stitching yarn. In case of the TFP based MRC Towpreg an average fiber volume content of 60 % leads to local fiber volume content up to 83 %. At such high local fiber volume contents the probability of directly contacted fibers increases significantly. In that case the load transfer between the fibers is limited. The roving material for the specimens investigated in [10] was placed on paper as base material with an average fiber volume content of 56 %. Due to the higher thickness and stiffness of the paper compared to the PA film the lower stitching yarn cannot compress the roving material on top of the base material. With the application of the flexible and thin PA film the carbon fibers are additionally deflected due to the displacement volume of the lower stitching yarn in the out of plane direction. Thus, the waviness is increased which results in a lower tensile modulus than the TFP specimens investigated in [10]. Furthermore, the alignment of the cutting device was not calibrated properly. Consequently, the fiber direction deflects up to 3° from the defined orientation. Additionally, despite a carefully conducted grinding process to remove the PA film, a slight damage of some fibers on the surface cannot be avoided.

Furthermore, it has to be mentioned that the values of the ideal unidirectional state (reference value) were calculated using the classical laminate theory based on the raw material data of fiber and matrix [11]. In real laminates the theoretical laminate properties are generally not fully achieved due to minimal misalignment and/or local stress concentrations in the clamping area. Thus, in practice a lower difference in modulus and strength of TFP based Towpregs can be expected compared to real produced unidirectional Towpreg laminates.

Taking into account the inhomogeneous fiber volume content the transverse strength values are comparatively good. The fracture behavior is similar compared to TFP produced unidirectional CFRP based on dry rovings.

4 CONCLUSION

In this work the process ability of epoxy pre-impregnated carbon fiber roving material (Towpreg) in the Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP) technology has been proven. Of the two Towpreg materials investigated only the MRC Towpreg was suitable for the TFP process at ambient conditions (25 °C). Compared to the TCR Towpreg the tack of the MRC Towpreg was considerably lower while maintaining a sufficient flexibility of the roving for the placement process. With the MRC Towpreg no matrix material is deposited on the needle and the maximal process speed is comparable to the TFP process with dry roving material.

Even though the TCR Towpreg was not usable at the given conditions it has to be mentioned that TCR material might be suitable for the TFP process if used at lower temperatures. When the TCR roving is cooled down just around 5 K to 20 °C it is significantly less tacky and the tendency of the matrix accumulation on the Towpreg surface is non-existent anymore.

The resulting material properties and the fracture behavior are comparable to TFP produced unidirectional CFRP based on dry roving material. Due to the TFP induced inhomogeneity and waviness lower fiber volume content within the Towpreg of about 55 % would be preferable.

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